

FIGURE 2 | Effects of the A009 extract in combination with 5-fluorouracil (5-FU) on breast cancer cell lines. BT549 (A) and MDA-MB-231 (B) cells were pretreated with extract A009 (dilution 1:800) or hydroxytyrosol (Hyt) (same concentration as that present in the 1:800 diluted A009 extract), for 24 h. Later, the medium was replaced with 5-FU 100 μ M alone or in combination with A009 or Hyt for 48 and 72 h. Proliferation was detected by the MMT assay at the indicated time points. The experiments were performed in quadruplicate and repeated two times. Results are expressed as the mean of the absorbance normalized on the T0 \pm SEM, one-way ANOVA, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$, and **** $p < 0.0001$. A009 activity was enhanced by addition of chemotherapy towards breast cancer cells.

FIGURE 4 | Effects of the combination A009+chemotherapy on breast cancer spheroids. Single spheroids were generated by culturing 4×10^3 BT549 or MDA-MB-231 cells in nonadherent conditions. BT549 (A,B) and MDA-MB-231 (C,D) spheroids were treated with the combination of A009 extract + 5-FU or Doxo, A009 or drugs alone, for 3, 6, and 12 days. During the treatment kinetic, spheroid diameters were detected, and spheroid macrophotographs were captured. The experiments were performed in quadruplicate and repeated two times. Scale bar = 200 μm . Data are shown as mean \pm SEM, two-way ANOVA, $**p < 0.01$, $***p < 0.001$, and $****p < 0.0001$. A009 combinations with chemotherapy reduced size of breast cancer cell spheroids.

FIGURE 7 | Cardioprotective effects of A009 extract in zebrafish embryos. The cardioprotective effects of the A009 extract on chemotherapy-induced cardiotoxicity was investigated in zebrafish embryos. All experiments were performed on zebrafish embryos exposed to doxorubicin (3 µg/ml) alone, A009 (dilution 1:1,000, 1:500), or the combination of doxorubicin (µg/ml) and A009 (dilution 1:1,000, 1:500) for 48 h (A) and 72 h (B) post fertilization (hpf). Embryo micrographs for all the experimental conditions are shown. Data for cardiac area are shown as fold% increased over control. Data are shown as mean ± SEM, one-way ANOVA, ***p* < 0.01 and ****p* < 0.001. DOX, doxorubicin; A009 batch extract; NT, not treated. A009 combinations with chemotherapy were protective toward the heart.

